

Qiṣāṣ: A Misinterpreted Concept of Qur'an

Faizan Kirmani*

Abstract: This study critically analyses the Qur'anic, linguistic, and jurisprudential interpretations of *Qiṣāṣ* in Islamic law, specifically with reference to Qur'an Surah Al-Baqarah (The Heifer) (2:178) and its implications for remission rights in cases of Murder. Through comparative textual analysis, the study explores inconsistencies between Qur'anic injunctions and the popular notions of scholars regarding *Qiṣāṣ*. It finds that the Qur'an strictly confines *Qiṣāṣ* to Murder cases, without extending it to bodily harm, and restricts the right of its remission to the biological brother. The article analyses the applicability of *Qiṣāṣ* in cases extending outside murder, and secondly, who has the right to remit the sentence. Both topics have been examined via a comparative textual analysis of Qur'anic verses and juristic interpretations, with the aid of a series of structured questions posed to the official Fatwa Council of the United Arab Emirates (UAE). The denial of the UAE Fatwa Council to provide a direct Qur'anic justification for extending *Qiṣāṣ* to cases of bodily harm or allowing remission by any legal heir suggests an implicit acknowledgment that no explicit scriptural basis exists for such expansions. In conclusion, this study highlights the disconnect between Qur'anic injunctions and prevalent jurisprudence.

Keywords: *Qiṣāṣ*; Qur'an; Murder; Intentional Killing; Hurt; Jews; Retaliation

I. INTRODUCTION

It is an established fact that *Qiṣāṣ*, a concept of the Qur'an, is accepted by both Muslim and non-Muslim scholars alike as being universally applicable to cases of murder and bodily injury. It is viewed as an example of the philosophy of retributive justice, usually stated in terms of "an eye for an eye" or "just retaliation," e.g., Mohamed 'abdalla Selim El-Awa notes, "*Qiṣāṣ*" itself is divided into two categories: "*Qiṣāṣ*" for homicide (*fi'n-nafs*) and, "*Qiṣāṣ*" for wounding (*fi'ma dunan-nafs*).¹ Sahibzada Aqil Munir, Rabia Umar, and Aisha Rasool describe, 'There are two primary varieties of *Qiṣāṣ*. One is retaliation of a life for a life, while the other is retaliation for internal organs. Offenses against human life fall under the first category, whereas offenses causing injury other than death fall under the second'.² Absar Aftab Absar points out, '*Qiṣāṣ* crimes are recognized as harms primarily against the individual and pertain to homicide and bodily harm'.³ Dr. Muhammad Zahid narrates, "*Qiṣāṣ* is an Islamic term meaning 'retaliation in kind' or 'revenge', 'eye for eye' or retributive justice. *Qiṣāṣ* principle is available against the accused, to the victim or victim's heir when a

* Ph.D Law (Scholar), Dadabhoy Institute of Higher Education Karachi Pakistan. Email: faizankirmani@yahoo.com

¹ Mohamed 'abdalla Selim El-Awa, *Theory of Punishment in Islamic Law - A Comparative Study* (PhD thesis, University of London, 1972) 150 <<https://eprints.soas.ac.uk/Qiṣāṣ22/1/11010612.pdf>> accessed 21 March 2025.

² Sahibzada Aqil Munir, Rabia Umar and Aisha Rasool, 'Qisas and Diyat: A Critical and Analytical Study of Murder in Criminal and Islamic Law' (2023) VIII (1) *Global Legal Studies Review* 99, 100.

³ Absar Aftab Absar, 'Restorative Justice in Islam with Special Reference to the Concept of Diyya' (2020) 3 (1) *Journal of Victimology and Victim Justice* 38, 47.

Muslim is murdered, suffers bodily injury or property damage”.⁴ Tahir Wasti observes, ‘*Qisās* is divided into two categories: retaliation of life for a life, and retaliation for/of organs’.⁵ Susan C Hascall mentions, ‘Foucault’s ideas are compatible with both restorative justice ideals and the ideals of Islamic criminal jurisprudence in general, and in particular, the law of *Qisās* (a category of crime that includes intentional homicide and wounding)’.⁶ Ja’afar Agaji Abdullahi, Lawal Tambaya Ahmad, and Misbahuddeen Muhammad Bashir state, ‘*Qisās* means retaliation of injury for injury equal to murder by murder. It could also be seen as infliction of injury on the culprit equal to what he has done to the victim, or murder by murder, as he exactly murdered the victim.’⁷ Michael Mumisa, Mohammad Habbash, Taghreed Jaber, and Jacqueline Macalesher find, ‘*Qisās* (retaliation or retribution) laws follow the principle of ‘an eye for an eye’ or *lex talionis* and they cover murder or serious cases of intentional bodily harm’.⁸ Khan highlights, ‘*Qisās* encompasses offences of physical assault and murder, which are subject to retaliation on the choice of the victim or surviving heirs’.⁹ Mark Cammack indicates, ‘*Qisās* means “just retaliation” and deals with homicide and the infliction of bodily harm short of death’.¹⁰

In addition, the concept of *Qisās* is usually viewed as extending the right of retribution to the legal heirs of a victim in case of bodily injury or murder. e.g., Sahibzada Aqil Munir, Rabia Umar, and Aisha Rasool conclude, ‘The *Qisās* right is accessible to the injured or deceased victim and their legal representatives in their lawsuit against the offending party’.¹¹ Khan outlines, ‘*Qisās* also includes the right of the victim or his heirs to choose between retribution, pardon, or negotiated settlement’.¹² Mohamed 'abdalla Selim El-Awa studies, ‘For deliberate homicide, the punishment prescribed in the Qur’an was the killing of the culprit, or blood-money if the relative(s) of the victim did not demand '*Qisās*’’.¹³ Ja’afar Agaji Abdullahi, Lawal Tambaya Ahmad, and Misbahuddeen Muhammad Bashir explain, ‘in a case of willful murder, the heirs can remit the death sentence against the convict and accept blood money instead of the death sentence’.¹⁴ Susan C Hascall records, ‘*Diyah* is defined as ‘a fixed amount of money paid to a victim of bodily hurt or to the deceased’s legal heirs in

⁴ Muhammad Zahid, ‘Justice System of Islam in the Form of Qisas, Diyat and Harabah for the Protection of Human Dignity’ (2019) 1 (1) International Research Journal on Islamic Studies 1, 7.

⁵ Tahir Wasti, *The Application of Islamic Criminal Law in Pakistan: Sharia in Practice* (Leiden: Brill 2009) 12.

⁶ Susan C Hascall, ‘Restorative Justice in Islam: Should Qisas Be Considered a Form of Restorative Justice?’ (2011), 4 (1) Berkeley Journal of Middle Eastern & Islamic Law 35, 36.

⁷ Ja’afar Agaji Abdullahi, Lawal Tambaya Ahmad and Misbahuddeen Muhammad Bashir, ‘Jurisprudential Analysis of Qisas: The Views of the Maliki School of Jurisprudence’ (2024) 4 (3) Middle East Research Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences 84, 84.

⁸ Michael Mumisa, Mohammad Habbash, Taghreed Jaber and Jacqueline Macalesher, *Sharia law and the death penalty- Would abolition of the death penalty be unfaithful to the message of Islam?* (London: Penal Reform International 2015) 11.

⁹ Shehreyar Khan, ‘The Role of Qisas and Diyaat in Facilitating Honor Killings’ (2018) 2 (1) RSIL Law Review 38, 40.

¹⁰ Mark Cammack, ‘Islamic Law and Crime in Contemporary Courts’ (2011) 4 (1) Berkeley Journal of Middle Eastern & Islamic Law 1, 4.

¹¹ Munir and others (n 2) 100.

¹² Khan (n 9) 40.

¹³ El-Awa (n 1) 150.

¹⁴ Abdullahi and others (n 7) 86.

homicide cases'.¹⁵ Michael Mumisa, Mohammad Habbash, Taghreed Jaber, and Jacqueline Macalesher discover, 'The Qur'an encourages the victim (or their family) to forgive the perpetrator, and seek financial compensation (*diyyah* – sometimes called 'blood money') as an alternative to demanding retribution through execution as an act of charity or in atonement for sins'.¹⁶ Tahir Wasti reports, 'In the case of deliberate homicide, the punishment prescribed in the Qur'an is the killing of the offender or payment of blood money, if the legal heirs of the victim do not ask for *Qiyās*'.¹⁷ Niaz A Shah recounts, 'The Qur'an provides two options to deal with someone who is found guilty of intentional murder: *Qiyās* (i.e. that he/she be killed in the manner in which the victim was murdered) and forgiveness by the heir/s of the victim'.¹⁸ Dr. Muhammad Zahid maintains, "*Qiyās* is an Islamic term meaning 'retaliation in kind or revenge', 'eye for eye' or retributive justice. *Qiyās* Principle is available against the accused, to the victim or victim's heir when a Muslim is murdered, suffers bodily injury or property damage".¹⁹

The article focuses on the traditional understanding of *Qiyās* among scholars and identifies inconsistencies between Qur'anic commands and the prevalent jurisprudential interpretations. After this, the article explains the theory of *Qiyās* based on its Qur'anic, lexicographical, and jurisprudential aspects. It then scrutinizes Sūrah 'Al-Baqarah' (The Heifer) (2:178) in detail to ascertain if the Qur'an restricts *Qiyās* to murder cases only or includes bodily harm as well. The article also examines the Qur'anic command of who is qualified to grant pardon, that is, whether such a prerogative is for the victim's biological brother or may be given to other inheritors.

The central analytical framework is divided into two main branches: first, the applicability of *Qiyās* beyond cases of murder; and second, the identification of those entitled to remit the sentence. Both topics have been examined via a comparative textual analysis of Qur'anic verses and juristic interpretations, with the aid of a series of structured questions posed to the official Fatwa Council of UAE.²⁰ Although the Council initially replied, but on the progression of more questions it abstained to respond. Council could not present any Qur'anic evidence in support of extending *Qiyās* to physical injury cases or extending the remission rights other than victim's brother. The argument synthesises these conclusions to contend that the Qur'an restricts *Qiyās* to cases of homicide and grants the right of remission to the victim's brother only.

II. ANALYSIS OF THE VERSE

Since the present concept of *Qiyās* is attributed to have been taken from the Qur'an, thus it seemed expedient to engross into the Qur'anic verse related to *Qiyās*. It is said that Chapter 2 verse 178 primarily deals with the ordainments regarding *Qiyās*.²¹ Its translation is as follows:

¹⁵ Hascall (n 6) 68.

¹⁶ Mumisa and others (n 8) 13.

¹⁷ Wasti (n 5) 13.

¹⁸ Niaz A Shah, 'The Principle of 'qisas'' *DAWN* (Karachi: 1 November 2013) <<https://www.dawn.com/news/1053308>> accessed 30 May 2025.

¹⁹ Zahid (n 4) 7.

²⁰ Fatwa UAE, 'Official Website' (Fatwa UAE, 2024) <<https://Fatwauae.gov.ae/en/login>> accessed 24 January 2025.

²¹ As per Fatwa No. 169213 received via email from the official Fatwa Council of UAE.

“O ye who believe! the law of equality is prescribed to you in cases of murder: the free for the free, the slave for the slave, the woman for the woman. But if any remission is made by the brother of the slain, then grant any reasonable demand, and compensate him with handsome gratitude, this is a concession and a Mercy from your Lord. After this whoever exceeds the limits shall be in grave penalty.”²²

The gist of this verse is that;

- a) *Qiyās* (law of equality) is prescribed in cases of murder.
- b) Its remission can be made by the brother of the slain.

To delve into this premise, a series of questions was sent to the official Fatwa Council of UAE, and it has been kind enough to respond to the queries

A. Applicability of Qur’anic Injunctions of *Qiyās* on Cases Other Than Murder

The 1st question that was submitted to the Council was as ‘What does *Qiyās* mean? Please respond in the light of Qur’anic verses only.’

Fatwa:

“*Qiyās* is "retaliation in kind", or retributive justice. In Islamic law (*sharia*), the doctrine of *Qiyās* provides for a punishment analogous to the crime, that is punishing the offender with a punishment similar to what he did. *Qiyās* is the punishment for homicide and assault. Whenever a person causes physical harm or death to another, the injured or family of the deceased has the right to insist upon the punishment, accept monetary recompense, or forgive the offender. The punishment of *Qiyās* is mentioned in the Qur’an (Al-Baqarah, 178) (O you who have believed, prescribed for you is legal retribution for those murdered ...).”²³

In the above response to the meaning of *Qiyās*, it explains that it is "retaliation in kind" and recognizes its application in homicide and physical assault. The response also points out the choices provided to the victim or heirs: demanding retribution, accepting compensation, or forgiving.

The only Qur’anic verse cited to establish this all-encompassing interpretation is Qur’an, Surah ‘Al-Baqarah’ (The Heifer) (2:178), which, if perused thoroughly, reflects that it ordains *Qiyās* in cases of *Qatl*/Murder only. Although the *Fatwa* broadens the scope of application of *Qiyās* to cases of harm, too, it does not cite any Qur’anic authority in support of this extension. This means the issue remains open: on what Qur’anic reasoning is the extension of *Qiyās* to physical harm justified?

It is this very vagueness which justifies posing a 2nd question to the Council, in the following words:

²² Qur’an, Surah Al-’Baqarah’ (The Heifer) 2:178 [Abdullah Yousuf Ali (tr), ‘The Qur’an: Translation and Commentary By Abdullah Yousuf Ali’ (Madina: King Fahd Glorious Qur’an Printing Complex 1984)].

²³ As per *Fatwa* No. 169213 received via email from the official *Fatwa* Council of UAE.

"Apropos to my Question # 169213 While referring to Qur'an you quoted (Al-Baqarah, 178). This verse ordains *qisās* for *qatl*/killing cases only while you opined that:

Whenever a person causes physical harm or death to another.

Based on (Al-Baqarah, 178), is it right to say that as per Qur'anic verses, *Qisās* is ordained for *qatl*/killing cases only and not for inflicting physical harm or hurt to another?"

Fatwa:

"Punishment by *Qisās* is also applied in cases of physical harm, as evidenced by verse (45) of Surah Al-Ma'idah, { And We ordained for them therein a life for a life, an eye for an eye, a nose for a nose, an ear for an ear, a tooth for a tooth, and for wounds is legal retribution... }, and we explained to you in a previous *Fatwa* (No. 147996) that this is called "*Shariah* of those before us". "*shar'a man qablana*". A law in the previous scriptures is applicable to us if there is no indication that it has been abrogated."²⁴

The answer relies on a verse from Qur'an Surah 'Al-Ma'idah' (The Table Spread) (5:45), which explicitly provides *Qisās* in cases of bodily harm and physical injury, i.e., eye for an eye. However, it is pertinent to mention that when this verse ordains an eye for an eye, it uses the word "them" in Arabic عَلَيْهِمْ, and as per the context of this verse, it discusses Jews. For its clarification, the following 3rd question was asked to the Council 'Is it right to say that in Chapter 5 Verse 45 the word عَلَيْهِمْ refers to Jews?'

Fatwa:

'Yes, this is true, and it is clear from the context of the speech, and you can find this in the *tafseer* of the verse in all the books of interpretation.'²⁵

The response ensures that the pronoun "عَلَيْهِمْ" in Qur'an Surah 'Al-Ma'idah' (The Table Spread) (5:45), is directed to the Jews, meaning that the command discussed there, "a life for a life, an eye for an eye..." was initially ordained to the Children of Israel.

In view of this, it raises the question that if these ordainments had been directed expressly to an earlier nation, and not specifically to the Muslim *Ummah*, then what is the legal rationale for its applicability in Islamic law today, more especially when it comes to bodily harm or physical injury?

In addition, if Muslims are to draw legal verdicts from this verse, it seems logical that there should be certain evidence that such verdicts have been reaffirmed in the *Shariah* revealed to Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him), and not merely from the laws revealed to previous nations. Otherwise, applying such ordainments universally may distort the line distinguishing what was specifically intended for previous nations and what has been legislated anew for the Muslim *Ummah*. For its clarification, the following 4th question was asked to the Council,

²⁴ As per *Fatwa* No. 169671 received via email from the official *Fatwa* Council of UAE.

²⁵ As per *Fatwa* No. 145704 received via email from the official *Fatwa* Council of UAE.

‘Apropos to my Question # 169671, Is there any Qur’anic verse ordaining that law in the previous scriptures is applicable to us if there is no indication that it has been abrogated?’

Fatwa:

"This is one of the legal rules that most scholars have agreed upon, and they have deduced it from several Qur’anic evidence, such as the verse:

{Those are the ones whom Allah has guided, so take an example from their guidance.
} [Al-An'am: 90]

And the verse:

{He has ordained for you of religion what He enjoined upon Noah and that which We have revealed to you, [O Muhammad], and what We enjoined upon Abraham and Moses and Jesus} [Al-Shura: 13]

And other evidence that you can find in books on the principles of jurisprudence.”²⁶

The above *Fatwa* brings some significant implications. If, as the response implies, the directions of previous scriptures are presumed to be valid unless there is a clear abrogation, then it raises questions about many religious practices being observed by Jews and Christians today. Many of these practices are ascribed by them to have been taken from the Bible. This also invites the possibility of examining which among these modern practices, presented as derived from Biblical teachings, may remain valid or pertinent within an Islamic legal system.

The absence of explicit Qur'anic or Prophetic confirmation or abrogation throws some doubt on how such practices are to be interpreted or approached in Islamic jurisprudence. Keeping in view the notion, the following 5th question was asked to the Council, ‘Apropos to my question # 169985, if you opine that law in the previous scriptures is also applicable to Muslims then may Muslims drink alcohol since it's drinking is permitted in Christianity as well as in Judaism?’

Fatwa:

"Your question number 169985 was as follows: (Is there any Qur’anic verse ordaining that "law in the previous scriptures is applicable to us if there is no indication that it has been abrogated?). Your question is related to previous questions in which we explained to you this legal rule, and if you read it carefully, you will notice that it does not apply to alcohol because there is evidence in our law indicates its prohibition. Assuming that alcohol is permissible in Christianity and Judaism, (there is strong doubt about this assumption) it is clear that this ruling is abrogated in Islam.”²⁷

The above *Fatwa* confirms that while alcohol may not have been explicitly prohibited in Christianity and Judaism, this has no bearing on Islamic law, Based on this argument, the following 6th question was sent to the Council:

“Apropos to my question # 170687, the reply led me to deduce that drinking alcohol is not prohibited in Christianity and Judaism and it is abrogated in Islam, so now it is

²⁶ As per *Fatwa* No. 169985 received via email from the official *Fatwa* Council of UAE.

²⁷ As per *Fatwa* No. 170687 received via email from the official *Fatwa* Council of UAE.

prohibited for Muslims. I am to ask, why this analogy can't be applied to *Qisās* ordainments namely in previous *Shariahs* (For Jews) there was *Qisās* a life for a life, an eye for an eye, a nose for a noseSo Islam abrogated all, except *Qisās* for *Qatl* cases, and now Muslims can claim *Qisās* for *Qatl* cases only?"

Fatwa:

“There is no evidence that *Qisās* was abrogated.

In our *Fatwa* to your previous questions, we mentioned the rule ("law in the previous scriptures is applicable to us if there is no indication that it has been abrogated?). And there is evidence in our law that indicates the prohibition of alcohol, so it is forbidden. As for *Qisās*, there is no evidence that it was abrogated. So, your saying that (Islam abrogated all, except *Qisās* for *Qatl* cases) there is no evidence for it, and Allah knows best.”²⁸

It can be seen that the answer is a bit vague and needs to be explained in greater detail. The question tried to compare the handling of alcohol and *Qisās* within the framework of previous divine legislation and their applicability in Islam. Specifically, it asked whether, just as Islam abrogated the allowance of alcoholic drinks contained in previous scriptures and substituted it with prohibition, it might have done the same with the law of *Qisās* i.e., keeping it for cases of *Qatl* (Murder) only but not extending it to non-lethal injuries like those to the eye, nose, or ear, as delineated in previous *Shari'ahs*.

The objective to pose such question was to determine if there is any evidence, textual or jurisprudential, that suggests the application of *Qisās* in non-lethal wounds, as provided in earlier scriptures, was confirmed, modified, or limited in Islamic law. Although the answer declared that there is no abrogation evidence, it failed to explain if *Qisās* for non-lethal wounds is still applicable in Islamic jurisprudence, or how it is interpreted and applied in practice. Since the answer was not clear, the following 7th question was sent to the Council:

“Apropos to my question # 169671. Appended please find my file containing two tables and kindly tell me why there is no synchronicity in Islamic jurisprudence with respect to the applicability of the doctrine of *shar' man qablana* which is evident from these two tables.”

These were the Tables:

Table-A

Ordainments	Judaism	Islam	Jurisprudence
<i>Qisās</i> (Retaliation)	As per Qur'an eye for an eye	As per Qur'an for <i>Qatl</i> cases only	Doctrine <i>shar' man qablana</i> has been applied i.e. Eye for an eye resultantly now <i>Qisās</i> (Retaliation) has been extended to the hurt cases too

Table-B

Ordainments	Judaism	Islam	Jurisprudence
--------------------	----------------	--------------	----------------------

²⁸ As per *Fatwa* No. 171411 received via email from the official *Fatwa* Council of UAE.

Drinking Alcohol	Permitted	As per Qur'an ordained to be avoided	Doctrine <i>shar'a mann qablana</i> is not applied and drinking alcohol is considered <i>haraam</i>
------------------	-----------	--------------------------------------	---

Fatwa:

“The sharia *Fatwa*

The fundamental principle. "Is the law of those before us applicable to us?"-although it is a matter of scholarly disagreement-applies to cases where it is established in our *Shari'ah* that it was a law for the prophets before us. and where no specific ruling exists in our *Shari'ah* regarding that matter. However, if it is not established in our *Shari'ah*, or if a specific ruling for us has been revealed, then it does not fall under this principle. May Allah guide you.

Scholarly Opinions:

The disagreement among scholars on whether the law of those before us is binding for us pertains only to matters that have been confirmed in our *Shari'ah* as laws prescribed for the previous prophets, without any explicit call for us to follow them. In such cases, there is evidence or guidance in our *Shari'ah* to emulate them. However, if something is known to have been a law for previous prophets only through the statements of their nations, it is not considered binding upon us by consensus. Likewise, there is no disagreement regarding what has been directly commanded in our *Shari'ah*, such as the meaning of the verse:

"And We decreed for them in it: a life for a life." (Qur'an 5:45). [Source: *Nashr al-Bunud "ala Maraqi al-Su"ud*, 2/24]²⁹

The answer, again, lacks clarity and is not directly targeted at the expressed concern. It was intended to point out what seems to be a glaring inconsistency in how the doctrine of *Shar'a man qablana* is applied within Islamic jurisprudence, illustrated through two comparative tables , one involving *Qisās* and the other involving the alcohol prohibition.

The answer seems to clarify the general outline of academic disagreement over the application of past legislation but fails to adequately reconcile the two particular examples given. It is not made clear whether the expansion of *Qisās* to non-fatal wounds is truly a product of *Shar'a man qablana*, or whether it has been independently concluded in Islamic law. Again, the justification for not applying the principle in the case of the prohibition of alcohol is not adequately clarified. Since again the answer was not clear, that's why the following 8th question was sent to the Council:

“Ref: Application WEB2974

As per Qur'an for Jews, there was *Qisās* as an eye for an eye, while as per Qur'an *Qisās* is for *Qatl* cases only, but jurists have extended *Qisās* for hurt cases too on the doctrine of *shar'a mann qablana* (Doctrine)

And

²⁹ As per *Fatwa* No. WEB 2974 received via email from the official *Fatwa* Council of UAE.

Drinking Alcohol is permitted in Judaism but Qur'an ordains to avoid it, here jurists don't apply the Doctrine and consider it *Haraam*.

There is no synchronicity in the application of Doctrine.

In which above case the application of Doctrine is wrong?"

The same was answered in the following words:

Fatwa:

"We thank you for reaching out to us and apologize for not being able to provide a *Fatwa* for your question. We have clarified that the *Fatwas* issued by the council on the platform you are currently using are designated for personal inquiries. Research-based or public interest related *Fatwas* are not addressed through this platform."³⁰

In light of the above *Fatwas*, it may be justly deduced that:

1. Qur'anic Evidence Limits *Qisās* to *Qatl* Cases Only, since in Qur'an Surah 'Al-Baqarah' (The Heifer) (2:178) the Qur'an explicitly ordains *Qisās* for murder but does not extend it to cases of physical injury.
2. Referring Qur'an Surah 'Al-Ma'idah' (The Table Spread) (5:45) for extending *Qisās* is contextually flawed. This verse specifically refers to Jewish law and uses the pronoun عَلَيْهِمْ (for them, i.e., Jews). Hence, applying it to Islamic jurisprudence is a sheer violation of the clear Qur'anic distinction.
3. Selective Application of Doctrine "*Shar'a mann qablana*," i.e., ordainments of previous scriptures are also applicable upon Muslims unless abrogated, is inconsistently being applied in Islamic Jurisprudence. It is being used to justify extending *Qisās* to hurt cases without considering that this would open the doors of applicability of several other ordainments upon Muslims, like drinking of Alcohol, which was permitted in previous scriptures.

B. Who May Remit the Sentence?

The term in the verse in question, which authorizes only the brother of the slain person to remit *Qisās*, uses the term أَخِيه. So, for its investigation following 1st question was sent to the Council, 'What are the meanings of the Arabic word أَخِيه? Explain as more as they could be.'

Fatwa:

'The meaning of this word (أَخِيه) is: (his brother).'³¹

In light of the above *Fatwa*, 2nd question was sent to the Council, 'Apropos to my question 167549, may I deduce that in the light of Qur'anic verse 2:178, only a brother of a slain person is competent to grant remission.'

³⁰ As per *Fatwa* No. WEB 3123 received via email from the official *Fatwa* Council of UAE.

³¹ As per *Fatwa* No. 167549 received via email from the official *Fatwa* Council of UAE.

Fatwa:

“Those who have the right to pardon are the heirs of the victim. Concerning the meaning of the word (أخيه - his brother) in the verse (But whoever overlooks from his brother anything, then there should be a suitable follow-up and payment to him with good conduct.) . The word " أخيه - his brother" means: the brother of the murdered or the victim himself, (the brotherhood here is the brotherhood of faith), and those who have the right to pardon are the heirs of the victim, any of them can pardon the killer and demand no *Qisās*.”³²

The *Fatwa* can be valued for its explication, specifically the explanation of the word "أخيه" (his brother) in Qur’an Surah ‘Al-Baqarah’ (The Heifer) (2:178), as alluding to spiritual brotherhood and not blood relationship. But this opens up the question further: If the word "brother" in this verse is interpreted as meaning common Muslim brotherhood (i.e., spiritual brotherhood), then why is the right of remission strictly limited to the statutory heirs of the victim?

This leaves a significant jurisprudential question: If "brotherhood" is given its broad sense, is the category of those who can pardon larger than heirs alone, or is this brotherhood in a spiritual sense only to be used as a moral symbol, not as a term of legal delegation? Additional clarification of this differentiation between the theological and legalistic uses of words was needed to clarify the misunderstanding between the figurative employment of "brother" and the enforceable privileges to particular individuals under Islamic law.

Since the *Fatwa* had opened the door to pose a new question in the light of the notion of *brotherhood*, here is the *brotherhood of faith*, so for its clarification, 3rd question was sent to the Council:

“Apropos to my question 167980. If you suggest that "the brotherhood here is the brotherhood of faith" then as per Qur’an all Muslims of the world are entitled to grant remission. I am to ask that on which basis you deduced that "and those who have the right to pardon are the heirs of the victim, any of them can pardon the killer and demand no *Qisās*.”

Fatwa:

“We repeat here, with more explanation, what we said in *Fatwa* 167980 regarding the meaning of the word (أخيه) in the verse, (But whoever overlooks from his brother anything, then there should be a suitable follow-up and payment to him with good conduct.) what is meant here by the word (أخيه = his brother) is the brother of the murdered (real brotherhood) or the victim himself, (faith brotherhood, see Surah Al Hujurat verse 10) and those who have the right to pardon are the heirs of the victim, any of them can pardon the killer and demand no *Qisās*, because pardoning *Qisās* entails paying blood money to the family of the murdered, who are the heirs, so everyone who has a right to inheritance has a share in the blood money.”³³

³² As per *Fatwa* No. 167980 received via email from the official *Fatwa* Council of UAE.

³³ As per *Fatwa* No. 168440 received via email from the official *Fatwa* Council of UAE.

The above *Fatwa* also appears to conflate two different interpretations of the term “أخيه” (his brother) in Qur’an Surah ‘Al-Baqarah’ (The Heifer) (2:178), first suggesting it could refer to real brotherhood (i.e., biological relation), and then alternatively citing spiritual brotherhood, as referenced in Qur’an Surah ‘Al-Ḥujurāt’ (The Inner Apartments) (49:10). Yet, the conclusion provided that only the statutory heirs of the victim are entitled to grant remission, seems to rely solely on inheritance law rather than directly on the term “his brother” as used in the verse.

This raises a need for further clarification: If “أخيه” (his brother) is interpreted as referring to all believers (faith brotherhood), then a textual or juristic basis is needed to explain why only the heirs are legally empowered to pardon. Conversely, if it refers to a biological or familial relationship, then the wording itself would seem to narrow the scope to a specific relative, not all heirs. In addition, for more clarification on the term أخيه (his brother) another 4th question was also sent to the council, ‘Apropos to my question 167980 the root of the word أخيه is اخو. May you please refer anywhere in Qur’an that the word اخيه or the derivatives of root اخو has been used in the sense of "brotherhood of faith"?’

Fatwa:

“We repeat here, with more explanation, what we said in *Fatwa* 167980 regarding the meaning of the word (أخيه) in the verse, (But whoever overlooks from his brother anything, then there should be a suitable follow-up and payment to him with good conduct.) what is meant here by the word (أخيه = his brother) is the brother of the murdered (real brotherhood) or the victim himself, (faith brotherhood, see Surah Al Hujurat verse 10) and those who have the right to pardon are the heirs of the victim, any of them can pardon the killer and demand no *Qisās*, because pardoning *Qisās* entails paying blood money to the family of the murdered, who are the heirs, so everyone who has a right to inheritance has a share in the blood money.”³⁴

From the above *Fatwa*, it is interesting to know that the Council has eventually found that in the verse in question Qur’an Surah ‘Al-Baqarah’ (The Heifer) (2:178) “أخيه” (his brother) refers to the slain individual, meaning a biological or actual brotherhood, not a generic spiritual brotherhood between believers.

This explanation seems to contradict the previous interpretation, which used Qur’an Surah ‘Al-Ḥujurāt’ (The Inner Apartments) (49:10) as an indication of the potential for faith-based brotherhood. By assenting that the use in this place signifies the true brother of the martyr (i.e., real kinship), the Council has *de facto* revoked or set aside the general concept of faith-based brotherhood as a literal interpretation of “أخيه” (his brother) in this verse.

This recognition upholds the initial postulate that if “أخيه” (his brother) were understood strictly in terms of religious brotherhood, it would introduce a legal uncertainty as to who possesses the right to grant remission. By affirming that the term is used to refer to an actual brother, the category of those who are entitled to pardon remains in line with the Qur’anic exegesis.

³⁴ As per *Fatwa* No. 168441 received via email from the official *Fatwa* Council of UAE.

Although the Council had conceded that in the verse in question, brother means murdered (real brotherhood), for the sake of obtaining more clarity, the following 5th question was sent to the Council:

“Apropos to question number 168440. When you say that "what is meant here by the word (أخيه = his brother) is the brother of the murdered (real brotherhood)". This makes firm my postulate that under Qur’anic verse 2:178 "only a brother (which now you have admitted a real brother) of a slain person is competent to grant remission". Moreover, you could not find anything in Qur’an, in support of your claim "and those who have the right to pardon are the heirs of the victim" Am I right?”

Fatwa:

“We repeat what we said in our answer, that those who have the right to pardon are the heirs of the victim. The Prophet (ﷺ) said: "Whoever kills deliberately, he will be handed over to the heirs of the victim. If they want, they may kill him, or if they want, they may accept the blood money" (*Sunan Abi Dawud*).

For further clarification of this issue, you should read about it in jurisprudence books (*Fiqh*).”³⁵

It can be clearly observed that in supporting the answer to the question, the Council has referenced a Hadith from *Sunan Abi Dawud* in order to state that the right of pardon belongs to the heirs of the victim. Although such narration is a significant legal foundation, it can also be observed that the Council had not referenced a direct Qur’anic verse in order to provide the statement that all heirs possess this right.

This is important, since the initial question posed quite categorically whether or not the Qur’an Surah ‘Al-Baqarah’ (The Heifer) (2:178) limits the right of remission to the "brother" of the slain, as is clearly stated within the verse. By first establishing that “أخيه” (his brother) means the actual brother and then justifying the wider legal extension on the basis of Hadith and not the Qur’an itself, the Council has, in effect, confirmed that the legal extension to all heirs stems from Prophetic tradition rather than from the Qur’anic text itself.

1. Discussion

The progression of *Fatwas* issued by the Council, based on successive inquiries, highlights key points of contention regarding the linguistic, theological, and jurisprudential understanding of this verse.

a. The Linguistic Argument – Defining "Brother" (أخيه)

The initial inquiry (*Fatwa* 167549) sought the meaning of أخيه, to which the Council responded that it simply means “his brother” in Arabic. However, in subsequent responses (*Fatwas* 167980, 168440, 168441), the Council introduced the notion that the term could refer to:

i. Real brotherhood (i.e., the biological brother of the victim).

³⁵ As per *Fatwa* No. 169043 received via email from the official *Fatwa* Council of UAE.

- ii. Brotherhood of faith (i.e., all Muslims).

While the reference to "faith brotherhood" was supported by an analogy to Qur'an Surah 'Al-Hujurat' (The Inner Apartments) (49:10), no direct evidence was presented from the Qur'an to suggest that أخيه in 2:178 refers explicitly to faith-based brotherhood.

b. The Jurisprudential Position – Who Can Pardon?

- i. The Council ultimately upheld the prevailing *fiqhi* (jurisprudential) position that heirs of the victim (rather than exclusively the biological brother) are entitled to grant remission or demand *Qisās* (*Fatwa* 169043).
- ii. The rationale behind this stance has been derived from Hadith (A tradition of the Prophet Mohammad³⁶), i.e., *Sunan Abi Dawud*, a collection of such traditions, which says that the victim's heirs have the right to either demand execution or receive blood money.
- iii. The Council remained adamant in their interpretation despite conceding that the Qur'anic verse being referenced uses the term "brother" in the singular form and failed to allude to a direct reference from the Qur'an to justify the application of this authority to all heirs.

c. The Inconsistency in Interpretation

- i. The Council initially affirmed that "brother" in the verse refers to real brotherhood, but later reverted to the broader interpretation that all heirs are entitled to grant remission.
- ii. The lack of a Qur'anic reference for extending the right to all heirs contradicts the explicit wording of 2:178, which limits the authority to "his brother" (singular).

2. Analysis

In short, it may be deduced that:

- a. The Qur'anic text explicitly mentions "brother," not "heirs," as the party entitled to grant remission.
- b. The Council's reliance on Hadith rather than the Qur'an for justifying the heirs' right to pardon suggests an external jurisprudential influence rather than a direct Qur'anic mandate.
- c. The contention that "brother" in this context is a faith-based brotherhood is not supported by the Qur'an and contradicts the actual meaning of brotherhood acknowledged by the Council.
- d. Accordingly, the Qur'anic passage 2:178, when strictly read based on its wording, suggests that the biological brother alone of the killed individual has a right to remit *Qisās*.
- e. Islamic jurists have extended the right to remit *Qisās* to all heirs, in the light of Hadith, but not taking reference directly from the Qur'anic text.

³⁶ On every occasion in this article where reference to Prophet/Messenger Mohammad appears, words "Peace Be Upon Him" shall be assumed.

III. CONCLUSION

The exegesis of Qur'an Surah 'Al-Baqarah' (The Heifer) (2:178), along with its linguistic implications, and jurisprudential interpretations, unveils significant disparities between scriptural evidence and classical Islamic jurisprudence on the imposition of *Qisās*. The verse specifically limits *Qisās* to *Qatl* (Intentional killings) cases only and it has been found that there is no direct Qur'anic evidence extending *Qisās* to bodily injury cases.

Invoking Qur'an Surah 'Al-Ma'idah' (The Table Spread) (5:45) to apply *Qisās* to bodily injury cases is contextually erroneous as the verse contains commandments specifically addressed to Jews and is therefore not binding upon Muslims.

As to the right of remission, the Council maintained the *fiqhi* (jurisprudential) position that the victim's heirs (not merely the biological brother) are entitled to extend remission, which is against the injunction of Qur'anic verse in question, which empowers as such to brother of the slain "his brother" (أَخِيهِ). The use of jurisprudential precedents over direct Qur'anic evidence indicates that *Qisās*, as practiced today, is influenced more by Prophetic traditions than by the primary source of Islamic legislation, i.e., Qur'an³⁷.

The refusal of the Council to provide an explicit Qur'anic basis for expanding *Qisās* to a broader scope outside of Murder cases reflects a *de facto* admission that no such direct Qur'anic evidence exists, thereby attracting the principle of "Qui tacet consentire videtur" (silence equals consent).

In addition, the Council did not outrightly deny the postulate that there is no verse in Qur'an granting the right to pardon in *Qisās* cases to the heirs of the victim³⁸, confirming its validity in the light of "Qui non negat, fatetur" (he who does not deny, admits).

In summary, though Islamic jurists extend *Qisās* to its wider application, this extension is merely based on Hadith and not on the Qur'an, which is the primary source of Islamic legislation.

Bibliography

Abdullahi, Ja'afar Agaji, Lawal Tambaya Ahmad and Misbahuddeen Muhammad Bashir, 'Jurisprudential Analysis of Qisas: The Views of the Maliki School of Jurisprudence' (2024) 4 (3) *Middle East Research Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences* 84.

Absar, Absar Aftab, 'Restorative Justice in Islam with Special Reference to the Concept of Diyya' (2020) 3 (1) *Journal of Victimology and Victim Justice* 38.

³⁷ A question "is it right to say that Quraan is the primary source of Islamic legislation?" was asked on the online portal of Mr. Al-Sayyid Ali Al-Husseini Al-Sistani, available at <https://www.sistani.org/english/send-question/>. The response was affirmative.

³⁸ See the last question marked as 169043 and *Fatwa* thereon which was received via email from the official *Fatwa* Council of UAE.

- Cammack, Mark, 'Islamic Law and Crime in Contemporary Courts' (2011) 4 (1) *Berkeley Journal of Middle Eastern & Islamic Law* 1.
- El-Awa, Mohamed 'abdalla Selim, *Theory of Punishment in Islamic Law – A Comparative Study* (PhD thesis, University of London, 1972) <https://eprints.soas.ac.uk/11010612/> accessed 21 March 2025.
- Hascall, Susan C, 'Restorative Justice in Islam: Should Qisas Be Considered a Form of Restorative Justice?' (2011) 4 (1) *Berkeley Journal of Middle Eastern & Islamic Law* 35.
- Khan, Shehreyar, 'The Role of Qisas and Diyaat in Facilitating Honor Killings' (2018) 2 (1) *RSIL Law Review* 38.
- Mumisa, Michael, Mohammad Habbash, Taghreed Jaber and Jacqueline Macalesher, *Sharia Law and the Death Penalty – Would Abolition of the Death Penalty Be Unfaithful to the Message of Islam?* (Penal Reform International, London 2015).
- Munir, Sahibzada Aqil, Rabia Umar, and Aisha Rasool, 'Qisas and Diyat: A Critical and Analytical Study of Murder in Criminal and Islamic Law' (2023) VIII (1) *Global Legal Studies Review* 99.
- Shah, Niaz A, 'The Principle of "qisas"' *DAWN* (Karachi, 1 November 2013) <https://www.dawn.com/news/1053308> accessed 30 May 2025.
- Wasti, Tahir, *The Application of Islamic Criminal Law in Pakistan: Sharia in Practice* (Brill, Leiden 2009).
- Zahid, Muhammad, 'Justice System of Islam in the Form of Qisas, Diyat and Harabah for the Protection of Human Dignity' (2019) 1 (1) *International Research Journal on Islamic Studies* 1.